

Paper 12

ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION IN COMMERCE BRINGS TRANSFORMATION IN THE PERFORMANCE LEVEL OF THE STUDENTS

Ravisha B.*, Sowjanya B., Ms. Nanditha Sunil*****

*Asst Professor, MSNM Besant Institute of PG Studies, Bondel, Mangalore .

Email: ravishab21@yahoo.com

**Student, MSNM Besant Institute of PG Studies Bondel, Mangalore

***Asst Professor, MSNM Besant Institute of PG Studies, Bondel, Mangalore .

Email: ravishab21@yahoo.com

Abstract

In India education has been accorded much importance since independence as it has been perceived that educational development is necessary to ensure economic and overall development of the country. Education is the one of the powerful weapon to develop the standards of the young population in the country. In India we can see that majority of the population is young generation but speaking on the percentage wise people have higher education is very minimum. Now it is the duty of us to find out what are the major causes that will hinders the young population to get higher education. Quality in higher education will build the qualitative resourceful young population to bring revolution in our country. This paper is build with an intension of to evaluate the impact of the higher education in the development part of the students. To give empirical touch as a researcher I collected 50 samples of respondents to get a clear picture about evaluation of performance of the students.

Key words: causes weapon and evaluate.

Introduction

Commerce and management stream has a sea of options and opportunities for those who want to make their career and achieve their goals in life. Students who are studying under this stream have an intellectual look towards the outside world. Commerce is like a wide tree it grown up well and branches of the tree spread near all surroundings of their and people are enjoying with its fruits.

In a general term commerce means it has spread its area like trade, banking, insurance, advertising, marketing, administrative, professionals like CA, teaching..etc. there is a lot of scope for the better employment if the students opt for the commerce. Choosing a career option mainly depends on the interest of the candidates. He has to know what his potential is and where he can best suit in the employment according to that he has to select the streams. Streams have their own option to develop their career in the job market.

As a profession, it is the duty of us to guide our students to create awareness among them these the areas of the commerce and if you want to work on the particular field means, you have to divert your thinking to that mode and build knowledge. Normally in the professional course students have to go for their project work in the companies or they have to work temporarily as an intern in some of the organization. In this case he will

come to know what type of work is going and how he has to involve in this procedure. Here senior person of the company will guide the intern regarding the various process of the company. So from this student will gain a practical knowledge about the industry which he is lagging in his academic year. This will makes the person more competent and build the confidence in work.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To analyse the career option under commerce stream.
- 2) To know the interest of students in commerce.
- 3) To develop the sufficient knowledge to make them employable.
- 4) To know the satisfaction level of their stream.

Methodology Applied

The research is developed through observation and collection of data through questionnaires. The sample size is determined as 50 students.

Statistical tool:

To analyze the data X^2 technique, correlation and bar chart is used and tried to bring conclusion from this analysis.

Performance indicator for the students

1) Knowledge

Through education we will come to know the various aspects of the different areas of the stream. That will helps to develop a new knowledge in the minds of the students and also helps to understand the basic.

2) Develop Professionalism

Higher education creates qualified professionals like CA, Managers, Industrialist and Academician etc. These are the courses that build professionalism in their career.

3) Identify career option.

The different sectors of the commerce and management can be identified easily if the person is educated. It makes easy to that person to select the particular job that he is interested most in that work.

4) Self employment

Under this discipline he has knowledge about each and every type of the industry and business. So there is a much scope for him to establish his own business or develop the small scale industry and create employment opportunity for the others.

5) Team work.

In each organization to perform better he has to work in a team. Industry recognises its efficiency through efficiency of their team. If you develop a good team work, that will prove your efficiency in your performance.

6) Strategy formulation.

To start any project, the basic requirement is they have to frame a strategy. According to the strategy they have to execute each and every aspect for implementing that plan. The role of a strategic planner will play major aspect in the industry.

7) Case Analysis

The present happening in the business world presented in the form of case. Students have to go through that live case and analyse it to bring solution to solve that case. Here students are come to know how to solve the problems that are daily issue in the industry.

8) Leadership

Inspiring the students by telling success stories of great leaders in the business field, will make the students to follow the footsteps of the leaders. This will encourage them to build leadership quality from the students day its self.

9) Risk analysis

Every business has to take risk to survive in the market. If the business man able to understand the risk that he has to take in the various segment of business then he will invest his capital through careful analysing various factors. This makes risk analysis will take crucial factor in the business.

10) Ethical Value

Each person has to develop ethical values in their trading or work. If you practice a good ethical practice in your business means, you will get a better return for your investment.

11) Communication :

To market your qualification and place in a good company communication will play major role. Commerce sector majorly depends on the public to understand the needs and convince of your client you require good communication.

12) Positive thinking

Commerce mainly depends on the market condition. If there is any fluctuation in the market will rectify in your work. There for students has to develop positive attitude in their work culture.

13) Technology Usage

Now in a modern world each work will depends on the technology. Up gradation of your skill to meet the requirement of sophisticated technology is must. To develop the career he must be very flexible to adopt the changing technology.

14) Presentation in Conference

Prepare the students to present the papers in the national and international seminar it will make the students to gain a new knowledge in different field and also helps to build confidence in the minds of the students.

15) Organize fest

Organizing a fest will guide the students in various aspects like train them as an organizer, handle responsibility, hospitality, time management etc.

16) Create interest on research

Students should be inspired by the faculty members to develop the research paper that will create value addition to themselves and the society.

17) Overview of Industry

Under this they will come to know the various levels of management. They have the opportunity to learn more on industry according to your preference, industrial knowledge makes the students easily place able in the market.

18) Work shop on aptitude skill:

At present in the job market we can see that for any type of the job aptitude exams are common. So to make our students strong in aptitude area we have to provide training to them to get success in the competitive exams.

Hypothesis: Conferences and seminars will encourage the students to gain more insight about subjects and generation of new knowledge to develop them self.

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total
Male	12	8	5	0	0	25
Female	16	6	3	0	0	25
Total	28	14	8	0	0	50

f_0	f_e	$(f_0 - f_e)^2 / f_e$
12	14	.2857
13	11	.3636
16	14	.2857
9	11	.3636
Total		1.2986

Here the X^2 value 1.298 falls under acceptance region there for accept the null hypotheses from this we can conclude that students taking seriously seminars and conferences to develop their career.

Hypothesis: There is a Sufficient guidelines required to place them better position.

Gender	Group Discussion	Knowledge	Presentation skill	Aptitude skill	Total
Male	22	24	24	25	95
Female	23	24	23	25	95
Total	45	48	47	50	190

f_0	f_e	$(f_0 - f_e)^2 / f_e$
22	22.5	.0111
24	24	0
24	23.5	.0106
25	25	0
23	22.5	.0111
24	24	0
23	23.5	.0106

25	25	0
		.0434

Here the X^2 value .0434 falls under acceptance region so accept the null hypothesis from this we can conclude that students requires Sufficient guidelines required to place them better position.

Interest of the students in the different fields of the commerce and management

Particulars	No of Respondents	% of Respondents
Banking	32	64
Insurance	3	6
MNC	6	12
Self employment	3	6
Media	2	4
Others	4	8
Total	50	100

Inference

From this graph it's clear that majority of the students are interested to join banking sectors because there is a lot of openings we can find at present in the banking sector

Higher education has to be focused on the present needs of the industry to meet the requirement of the various companies.

Particulars	Male (X)	Female (Y)	X ²	Y ²	XY
Strongly Agree	18	19	324	361	342
Agree	6	6	36	36	36
Neutral	1	0	1	0	0
Disagree	0	0	0	0	0
Strongly Disagree	0	0	0	0	0
Total	25	25	361	397	378

$$\begin{aligned}
 r &= \frac{n \sum XY - \sum X \times \sum Y}{\sqrt{\frac{n \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2}{n} \times \frac{n \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2}{n}}} \\
 &= \frac{5 \times 378 - (25 \times 25)}{\sqrt{(5 \times 361 - 25^2) \times (5 \times 397 - 25^2)}} \\
 &= \frac{1265}{\sqrt{1180 \times 1360}} \\
 &= \frac{1265}{1267} \\
 &= .9984
 \end{aligned}$$

From this analysis it's clear that there is a positive correction between X and Y variable it shows that higher education has to design the curriculum as per the needs of the industry.

Findings:

1. Higher education should help the students to develop basic foundation regarding the industry.
2. Seminars and workshops will help the students to gain more knowledge about the advanced issues in their stream.
3. Higher education prepares the students by dating their skills according to the present requirement of the job market.
4. Higher education should teach the students to cultivate team spirit in every work.
5. Commerce education develops more entrepreneurs to solve the unemployment problem.
6. Majority of the students opt for banking sector under commerce education.

Suggestion:

1. Higher education has to give opportunity to students to do the work in innovative way.
2. Higher education has to develop skill based training programme to the students.
3. Commerce education should adopt flexibility in designing syllabus according to the changes takes place in the present scenario.
4. Industrial visit helps the students to understand the day today activities of the company.
5. Students has to use latest techniques like e journal, e book, commerce and management related web sites these helps the students to develop their knowledge.

Conclusion

Now a days there is a lot of demand for commerce and management education so each institution has to make a strategy that how they can improve the commerce and management education to place their students in better position. Every institution has to give importance to develop soft skills of the students. That will help them to develop their career.

References

- Baiba Rivza and Ulrich Teichler, The Changing Role of Student Mobility, Higher Education Policy (2007) **20**, 457–475
- David E. Leveille, Accountability in Higher Education: A Public Agenda for Trust and Cultural Change. Research and Occasional paper series: A report, December 2006, pp 5 – 28
- Noe Ortega, The Role of Higher Education Associations in Shaping Policy That Connects Immigration to Educational Opportunity: A Social Capital Framework, Journal of Hispanic Higher Education January 2011 10: 41-65.
- Santiago Mengual-Andres, Rethinking the role of Higher Education, New approaches in educational research , Vol. 2. No. 1. January 2013. pp. 1–2.